

SIMULATION METHODOLOGY FOR IMPACT DAMAGE AND FAILURE OF AERO-ENGINE COMPONENTS MADE OF TEXTILE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A multi-scale modelling strategy is developed for predicting the constitutive behaviour of textile composites under impact loading with a view to their applications in fan blade containment casings of modern turbofan aero-engines, where the critical loading condition is the impact in the event of fan blade off (FBO). At a micro- and meso-scale, the unit cell modelling concept was employed to characterize the 3D composite material with a glass-fibre woven textile reinforcement, based on the mechanical properties of the constituent materials, fibres and resin, and structure and geometry of the textile weave. All the modelling parameters involved have a clear physical meaning and are quantifiable experimentally. In addition to that, forming process modelling has been carried out in order to provide a comprehensive solution to the design problem of composite components. In particular, the influence of the variability in the internal geometry of fabric on permeability of the fabric has been investigated.

Material characterization at micro- and meso-scales involves predictions of elastic and strength effective properties, and also incorporates progressive damage modelling. The validation of the models built is carried out by carrying out sanity checks and comparing the predictions with the coupon test data. Additionally, measured rate sensitivity data for the resin are presented and the procedure for assigning the rate-dependence to a textile composite is outlined. At a macro-scale, the composite is treated as a monolithic material, and its constitutive behaviour is predicted based on an artificial neural network (ANN) algorithm. Validation has been assessed with the simulation of a high rate impact on a composite plate and this is further developed to a mixed finite element model of an aero engine fan casing undergoing a blade-off event.

1 INTRODUCTION

At present, 3D textile composites are being studied extensively, as properties of these materials make them promising candidates for manufacturing structural components in aerospace applications. Unlike the conventional laminated composites, these lightweight materials show a strong resistance to delamination under impact loading or even eliminate delamination as a damage mechanism, while delamination is one of the most common failure causes in aerospace applications.

While modelling of laminated composites can be considered well-established, predicting mechanical response of composites based on woven/braded textile reinforcements is still an issue. Because of the anisotropy of the textile composites arising from a complex weaving architecture of the reinforcement, expressing the stress-strain relationship for these materials analytically, namely, by defining an appropriate stiffness tensor, is far from straightforward. For the same reason, definition of the failure conditions in form of failure envelopes based on a fixed number of parameters might not be applicable in this case. At the same time, in absence of the robust and reliable modelling methodology

which can be employed by engineers, characterization of these materials by means of mechanical testing would require an enormous amount of the experimental work. The model should be consistent and verifiable, and its input parameters should have a clear physical meaning and could preferably be defined using well-established testing techniques.

The simulation methodology for characterizing textile composites was developed at the University of Nottingham over the last few years. It employs a multi-scale analysis approach, treating yarns as unidirectional composites at a micro-scale level, while composite is considered as a monolithic material at a macro-scale. In order to generate the model for predicting the constitutive behaviour of the composite, information of its internal structure is required, along with the mechanical properties of the constituent materials, fibre and resin, which can be readily obtained from the supplier, or be determined from standard tests.

This paper describes the complete modelling process, starting with material characterization at micro-scale and meso-scale. The macroscopic constitutive behaviour of the material is defined based on artificial neural network (ANN) algorithm, the brief summary of which is also given in the paper. In order to facilitate the description, the modelling process is demonstrated for a composite based on specific textile reinforcement architecture, namely layer-to-layer angle interlock weave, the structure of which is shown in Fig. 1. Furthermore, to demonstrate the practicality of the model in real-life applications, and verify the model by comparing its predictions with the experimental data, a number of material tests has been carried out. For mechanical tests, composite panels were manufactured using vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding process, where the infusion system used was Prime20LV epoxy resin. E-glass fibre preform with layer-to-layer angle interlock weaving architecture was used as a textile reinforcement. Dry fabric characterization was carried out by appropriate processing of micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) images.

Figure 1: Layer-to-layer angle interlock fabric: (a) schematic drawing the regular structure; (b) micro-CT image.

2 MODELLING FRAMEWORK

2.1 Material characterisation at micro- and meso-scales

To describe the material constitutive behaviour at micro- and meso-scale, a unit cell (UC) analysis methodology was employed, where the material is represented by a simplest repeating unit of its structure.

Within the modelling methodology proposed here, the unit cell analysis is applied at two scales. Hexagonal unit cell as shown in Fig. 2a represents the yarns, which are treated as unidirectional (UD) composites at a micro-scale, while at a meso-scale, the unit cell as shown Fig.2b is employed, which explicitly defines the complex geometry of the fabric weave structure in a textile composite.

Unit cell based analysis may require a lot of effort, in particular, when a FE model of a unit cell is created. This involves definition of appropriate boundary conditions, as well as creating and meshing a model of a complex geometry for textile composite UCs. A fully automated material characterization toolbox UnitCells© has been developed at the University of Nottingham [1] to facilitate this process. UnitCells© is based on Abaqus/CAE as a platform. Within UnitCells©, a free open source code, TexGen [2] is called generate complex UC geometry, while Hypermesh [3] software is employed to generate the high-quality mesh, which is appropriate for the imposition of periodic boundary conditions. The boundary conditions follow from geometric symmetries present in the microstructure represented by the unit cell [4].

Figure 2: (a) Hexagonal unit cell for UD composite; (b) unit cell for textile composite with layer-to-layer interlock textile reinforcement.

UnitCells© contains a library of UCs for composites with various reinforcement architectures, ranging from UD composites to 3D textile composites based on woven and braided reinforcements. To calculate the effective properties for a particular type of composite, an appropriate UC is to be selected via the UnitCells© interface and the input parameters are to be specified, while the analysis is run automatically.

For a UD unit cell, the input parameters are the material properties of fibre and resin as specified by the supplier, and fibre volume fraction, V_F , within the warp and weft yarns. The properties of glass fibres and resin are given in Table 1, while the fibre volume fractions in the warp (78.6%) and weft (74.65%) yarns were estimated by analysing the micro-CT images of the fabric. The predicted elastic properties of the yarns are summarised in Table 2.

	Density ρ , kg/m ³	Elastic modulus E , GPa	Poisson's ratio ν	Tensile strength S_t , MPa	Compressive strength S_c , MPa
Resin (Prime 20)	1140	3.5	0.35	73	120
E-glass fibre	2570	74	0.22	2000	1080

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the constituent materials

	ρ , kg/m ³	E_1 , GPa	E_2 , GPa	G_{12} , GPa	ν_{12}	ν_{23}
Warp yarn (Hexagonal UC)	2264.0	58.86	22.93	8.39	0.2421	0.3276
Weft yarn (Hexagonal UC)	2207.5	56.08	19.62	7.13	0.2469	0.3437
Warp yarn (random fibre distribution)	2264.0	58.14	23.66	8.29	0.2402	0.2966
Weft yarn (random fibre distribution)	2207.5	55.51	20.88	7.10	0.2448	0.3154

Table 2. Elastic properties of the yarns

Hexagonal UC is an idealised representation of the material structure, as it is based on the assumption that the fibres are distributed regularly within the yarn. To assess the effect a non-uniform fibre distribution can have on predictions of material properties, a UC model with random fibre distribution was generated, as shown in Fig. 2 (c). The elastic material properties predicted with this model are given in Table 2. As can be seen, the predictions obtained with two models are very similar.

To characterize the material at a meso-scale, the analysis was carried out for the UC as shown in Fig. 2b. In this case, in addition to the material properties, which are the properties of resin as in Table

1 and parameters of the yarns as in Table 2, geometric parameters of the weave are to be specified. These were also determined by processing the micro-CT images of the fabric and they are given in Table 3.

	Width, mm	Height, mm	Spacing, mm
Weft yarn	1.447±0.087	0.357±0.036	4.520±0.39
Warp yarn	1.306±0.09	0.375	1.38

Table 3. Geometric properties of the weave

As a check of the accuracy of the model built, a total V_F and the weaving angle of warp yarn in the model were compared to their measured values. Measured weaving angle of $\sim 25^\circ$ was found to be in a good agreement with the 26.8° predicted value, and the predicted value of $V_F=48.52\%$ was found to be close to $V_F=51.2\%$ in 4.12 mm thick composite panels.

Modelling framework as described in the previous sections is developed assuming an idealized regular structure of the reinforcement. In real textile composites, however, some degree of geometric variability is inherent within fibrous reinforcements. Geometric variability can potentially affect the forming process and material performance. An initial study was carried out to investigate the influence of alignment of weft yarns on the mechanical behaviour of the composite. As can be seen from micro-CT image in Fig. 1(b), in the weave, the weft yarn cross-sections were not aligned vertically, but appear to be shifted in the same direction. Therefore, in addition to an idealised meso-scale UC model as shown in Fig. 3(a), a UC as shown in Fig. 3(b) was generated, where weft yarns were offset horizontally for more accurate representation of the real composite weaving structure.

Figure 3: Schematic drawings of meso-scale UC models: (a) UC with an idealized weave; (b) UC with weft yarns offset horizontally.

Effective elastic properties predicted with UCs as shown in Figs. 3(a) and 3(b) are listed in Table 4 along with the available experimental data. As can be seen, predictions of both UC models agree well with the experimental data. Furthermore, there is just a marginal difference between the values of elastic properties predicted by two models, hence it can be concluded that the horizontal offset of the weft yarn stacks does not have any significant effect on the mechanical performance of the composite.

	Elastic moduli, GPa						Poisson's ratios		
	E_1	E_2	E_3	G_{12}	G_{23}	G_{13}	ν_{12}	ν_{23}	ν_{13}
Predicted (idealised weave)	24.61	19.81	10.23	4.95	5.38	3.70	0.14	0.51	0.35
Predicted (weft yarn offset horizontally)	24.603	19.52	9.84	4.94	5.20	3.57	0.13	0.55	0.35
Measured	24.77±3.12	15.92±0.55		4.03±0.14					

Table 4. Effective elastic properties predicted from meso-scale UC analysis.

Having considered variability in terms of randomness in fibre distribution within yarns and distortion in weave pattern, it can be concluded that idealised models would serve as a good basis to facilitate design activities, given the range of variability in the results due to these factors.

Several case studies have also been conducted to investigate the influence of geometric variability on permeability of the fabric [5]. To characterise the fabric geometry, X-ray micro-CT was applied to obtain 3D images of a moulded composite sample. An image processing methodology was developed

to characterize the geometry of the yarns, such as yarn paths and cross sections, by analysing the 3D image slices. Two of the most obvious variability features were the horizontal offset of the weft yarns, which was mentioned above, and the varying height of the warp yarns cross-sections, which is relatively low at crossovers with weft yarns, where yarn compaction is high, and is substantially larger between the weft yarns. Unit cell models for idealized weave, weft yarn offset weave and weave with varying warp yarn cross-section were generated with TexGen software. The required internal geometry was reconstructed by modelling the yarn path and interpolating various yarn cross-sections along the yarn paths. The flow modelling was carried out with Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD) software.

The permeability predictions in the warp, weft and through thickness flow directions for all three models are compared in Fig. 4. Overall, predictions suggest that the highest permeability is associated with an idealised fabric structure, and introducing variability leads to permeability reduction. Whilst offsetting weft yarns does not cause a substantial reduction in permeability values, and even leads to a marginal increase in permeability in warp flow direction, the varying warp yarn height substantially reduces the permeability in all three flow directions.

Figure 6. Predicted permeability in three flow directions (column view).

The results of this preliminary study indicate that geometric variability can substantially affect the permeability of the textile perform. In current ongoing research, models with stochastic geometric variability will be generated. Specifically, the stochastic variations from the ‘average’ unit cell model will be considered in order to generate the model that accurately represents the real material. Furthermore, surface yarn deviation (e.g. overlapped warp yarns at the top surface and suspended weft yarns at the bottom surface) is to be taken into account. Once the modelling is finalised, the predictions will be validated against the permeability measured in the experiments.

2.2 Modelling composite damage and failure at micro and meso-scale

In composite materials, prior to the ultimate failure, which associated with formation of macro-cracks and a complete loss of load carrying capacity, a damage often develops in form dispersed micro-cracks. To quantify the degree of damage in the material and account for the variation in the effective material properties following the initiation and evolution of damage, a concept of continuum damage mechanics (CDM) is commonly employed.

In general, complete formulation of damage and failure in UD composites requires definition of the following:

- a) Damage representation relation – expressing stiffness as a function of damage variable to predict the stiffness reduction as the damage grows.

- b) Damage initiation condition to define the onset of damage. In UD composites, the conventional UD composite failure criteria can be used for this purpose.
- c) Damage evolution law, defining the evolution of damage variable once the damage is initiated.
- d) Ultimate failure condition that specifies material state when it may be considered to have failed.

In this work, CDM concept is applied to define the constitutive behavior within the textile composite yarns, which can be considered to be UD composites at a micro scale. At present, UnitCells© tool is equipped with capability to predict damage based on damage representation and damage evolution laws as proposed by Matzenmiller et al. [6] for UD composites under a plane stress. These were adapted to define damage in a general 3D stress case. The damage initiation is described according to failure criteria proposed by Hashin [7]. The effective strength is defined as a maximum stress value on the average strain-stress curve calculated under the unidirectional loading [8]. Applying UD unit cell analysis to the yarns, the strengths values of the yarns were determined as shown in Table 5.

	Longitudinal strengths, MPa		Transverse strengths, MPa		Shear strengths, MPa	
	tensile	compressive	tensile	compressive	longitudinal	transverse
Warp yarn	1580.70	894.60	55.84	88.32	56.66	33.69
Weft yarn	1506.64	824.23	57.78	89.09	58.71	35.61

Table 5. Predicted strengths of the yarns

At a meso-scale, damage can occur in both yarns and the matrix, hence in progressive damage model was introduced for the resin, too. Resin can be treated as an isotropic material, hence von Mises criterion was used to define the damage onset. Stiffness reduction due to damage and damage evolution were defined in a similar way as for the yarns, however instead of employing multiple damage variables defining stiffness degradation in transversely isotropic yarns, a single damage variable was sufficient to account for reduction of resin stiffness.

With damage and failure defined at for both yarns and resin, the accuracy of the meso-scale UC analysis predictions was assessed by comparing them with the experimental data captured in standard coupon tests. Both predicted and measured strength properties are summarised in Table 6, where the subscripts ‘1’ and ‘2’ refer to warp and weft weaving directions, and subscripts ‘t’ and ‘c’ denote the tensile and compressive loading.

	Effective strengths, MPa								
	S_{1t}	S_{1c}	S_{2t}	S_{2c}	S_{3t}	S_{3c}	S_{12}	S_{13}	S_{23}
Predicted	144.65	172.47	321.17	240.72	72.79	84.35	44.83	59.10	40.61
Measured	223.5±3.4	173.3±6.9	206.4±13.5	199.1±5.1			39.6±1.8		

Table 6. Effective strengths of the textile composite.

While good agreement was achieved between predictions of the effective elastic properties and experimental data, the predictions of the effective strengths are less accurate. This discrepancy is due to the definition of the input parameters. The input parameters affecting the calculation of the effective elastic properties were the material properties of fibres and resin, as well as geometric parameters of the fabric, which were measured explicitly. Hence the values of these parameters represented the actual constituent materials and weaving architecture of the composite. On the other hand, the parameters defining damage evolution were not based on measurements, and were assigned a single fixed value as a temporary measure to facilitate the development of the model. This affects the accuracy of predictions of stiffness degradation and hence the strengths of the material.

Definition of damage parameters at a micro scale is a challenging task, as macroscopic testing techniques for capturing progressive damage are not applicable in this case. Another issue is the appropriate definition damage representation and evolution, as in order to get reliable predictions of damage, a robust and consistent damage model formulation is required. Such approach was initially proposed by Talreja [9], and was later developed by Li et al. [10, 11] who derived the analytical expressions for damage related material constants, which are involved in definition of damage representation relations, and proposed the damage evolution law where damage variable is defined as a function of damage driving forces. The rigorous mathematical formulation for both damage representation and damage evolution was derived based on thermodynamics with internal variables with damage as an internal state variable. The damage model has been implemented as a computer code and was validated by applying it to predict damage in laminates based on various lay-ups [11], where each lamina was assigned the same set of material and damage parameters. In terms of damage parameters required, two damage initiation and two damage evolution parameters should be specified. The predictions were compared with data captured in tests performed on laminates of various lay-ups. Appropriate methods for determining damage initiation and damage evolution parameters have been devised. The comparison of experimental data and predictions confirmed that model allows for accurate capture of stiffness reduction due to damage in various types of laminates. With damage model being validated for UD composite analysis at a macro-scale, it is currently being applied to define the progressive damage within the yarns.

2.3 Macro-scale analysis methodology

Meso-scale unit cells as developed in previous sections can be used for material characterization under uniform loading conditions, hence the meso-scale analysis predictions may be directly compared to the experimental data obtained in standard coupon tests. However, it is impractical to apply meso-scale UC modelling in structural analysis under general loading conditions.

Damage and failure modelling is even more important issue when defining the constitutive behaviour of textile composites at a macro scale. For unidirectional composites, a large variety of strength criteria is available, which are commonly applied in laminate analysis. Failure is predicted based on failure envelopes constructed with a minimum set of strength properties, which are determined experimentally. However, this methodology is not directly applicable to textile composites, as devising a failure criterion in the conventional sense for these materials would be extremely challenging and may not be possible.

In this work, both of the issues as outlined above were tackled by applying ANN algorithm to define the constitutive behavior of the textile composite at a macro-scale [12]. ANN is essentially an advanced interpolation tool [13], where sampling points are defined as meso-scale UC analysis outcomes. Various loading combinations are applied to a meso-scale UC to evaluate the effective stress-strain relationships and capture the failure events. Sufficient amount of such points forms a finite data set, which is applied to train the ANN. After training, a well-structured database is generated, which contains information on parameters and structure of the ANN used. Via the user-defined subroutines, the database can now be accessed by Abaqus solver to predict the material response at a macro-scale. For this, FE model of the composite component is generated, where composite is treated as a monolithic material. The ANN database is imported into the user-defined material properties of the composite, and is accessed via the user defined subroutine at every increment, evaluating the stress state within the material corresponding to the given strain state.

With macroscopic material response being defined via ANN, structural deformation and failure can be predicted with sufficient assurance that micro and meso-scale material level damage and failure have been duly taken into account.

2.4 Rate dependency

When considering constitutive behaviour of the composite under impact, it is necessary to take into account strengthening of the material at high strain rates. In glass fibre reinforced composites, both of the constituents, the resin and the fibres, are rate-dependent, while in a carbon fibre reinforced composites, rate dependency arises mainly from rate sensitivity of the resin.

In the modelling framework presented here, the mechanical properties of the constituent materials are used explicitly, as described above, hence once the rate dependency of the constituents is known, it is assigned to the mechanical properties of these materials at micro- and meso- scale levels. To determine rate sensitivity of the yarns, a micro-scale analysis is employed, where a UD unit cell is loaded at different strain rates, effective properties are calculated, and rate sensitivity parameters related to the moduli and strengths of the yarns are extracted. Next, thus defined material properties are assigned to the yarns in a meso-scale model, along with the rate-dependent properties of the resin, and same analysis is carried out to determine the quantify the rate-dependency of the material at a meso-scale.

The rate sensitivity of the constituent materials is determined experimentally, by measuring the elastic and strength properties both at quasi-static loading as well as over a range of strain rates. Appropriate experiments have been carried out with the resin samples to determine its rate sensitivity under compression. The plots showing the Young's modulus and the strength measured at different strain rates are shown in Fig. 5(a) and 5(b), respectively. As can be seen, a relatively low rate dependency of the elastic modulus has been detected. A large scatter in the elastic modulus measurements arises from the complexity in extracting this quantity from Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar test data. On the other hand, compressive strength of the material shows a clear trend to increase with a strain rate. The strength value triples in a range of strain rates $[0.0004\text{s}^{-1}, 2443\text{ s}^{-1}]$.

Figure 5. Rate sensitivity of the epoxy resin: (a) Young's modulus; (b) compressive strength.

3 APPLICATION TO MODELLING THE COMPONENT FAILURE

To demonstrate the capability of the methodology developed for predicting damage and failure in textile composites at a macro-scale, and to carry out the initial assessment of the model predictions, the ballistic impact of the flat composite panel was simulated.

Ballistic test were performed on the plates cut out of moulded textile composite panel. Circular exposed area of the plates was 100 mm in diameter. Plates were impacted at a range of velocities by a steel ball of 12.7 mm in diameter. In each test, the incident (striking) velocity, V_i , and the residual velocity, V_r , were determined by post-processing the video recorded with the high-speed camera. Plots

showing V_r versus V_i as determined experimentally are shown in Fig. 4a. Limit velocity at which the projectile reliably penetrates a target was estimated to be ≈ 174 m/s.

A rigid body impact was simulated in Abaqus/Explicit. A FE model of a circular plate of the same dimensions as in the experiment was created. As a case study, an ANN was generated and trained, where both resin and fibres are assumed to be rate insensitive, and it was applied to predict the composite plate response under a rigid ball impact. Several impact cases were simulated, and rigid ball velocity time histories were calculated for each case as shown in Fig. 7. In both perforation and non-perforation cases, the rigid ball acquires the constant velocity, V_r , following the perforation of the plate/ ball rebounding from the plate. These residual velocities are plotted against the striking velocities in Fig. 6b.

For the case considered, the predicted limit velocity is substantially lower than the experimental value as was expected, since the ANN does not incorporate the rate sensitivity of the resin and fibres. Strain rate effects should provide a substantial contribution to the material strength in the ballistic tests, where the strain rates are high.

Figure 6. Incident velocity plotted against the residual velocity (a) experimental data; (b) predictions obtained with rate-independent model.

Figure 7. Predicted time histories of the velocities in rigid impact simulations.

Once the strain rate dependency is implemented into the model computer code, and the accuracy of the model is validated by comparing its predictions with the ballistic test data, the model developed will be applied to predict the damage and failure in large textile composite components. Specifically, it

will be applied for assess the impact resistance of the aero-engine containment casing manufactured from a woven textile composite. For this component, critical loading condition is the impact in the event of fan blade off (FBO).

One of the major issues in modelling the large scale components is the computational costs associated with a large number of finite elements required to adequately mesh the model. To tackle this issue, a mixed finite element type analysis procedure has been developed and applied to simulate the projectile impact on a cylinder representing a containment casing of the aero-engine [14]. A schematic drawing of an oblique impact test set up, which imitates an FBO event and is commonly used to assess the impact performance of a fan casing [15], is shown in Fig. 8(a).

A simplified FE model of the containment casing was generated, where the casing was represented by a cylinder with inner diameter of 2000mm, 750mm in height, with a wall thickness of 20mm. Two types of elements were employed to mesh the cylinder as shown in Fig. 8(b). Solid element mesh was applied to a quarter of the cylinder, near the site of the impact, while thin shell elements were used to mesh the remaining part of the cylinder. Impact simulations were carried out in LS-DYNA. The impactor is modelled as a rigid thin steel plate. The composite material constitutive behaviour in the solid element region was defined via the “built-in” material model MAT162 , while MAT58 was used to for the shell region. For comparison, impact cases were simulated where the composite cylinder was meshed with solid element only.

Figure 8. (a) Configuration of a composite casing impact test. (b) Finite element model with quarter of the casing ring modelled with solid elements.

The projectile trajectory, cylinder deformation and failure predicted for model with the mixed element mesh were similar to those obtained for the model generated with solid elements only. At the same time, an obvious improvement in computational efficiency was detected for the model with the mixed element mesh, as it nearly halved the computational resources and time required to run the impact case.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The modelling approach to predict impact damage and failure in textile composites has been presented in this paper. The procedure for characterizing material at micro-and meso scale via the UC analysis has been previously established. It is applied to generate the data points for development of an ANN system, which is employed to predict macroscopic behaviour of the composite material. This modelling methodology ensures that while the composite is defined as a monolithic material at a macro-scale, all its meso-scale features and damage characteristics are duly reflected.

The input parameters of the model are essentially the material properties of the constituent materials and geometric parameters of the reinforcement. Geometry of the textile reinforcement has been parametrised [1] for a range of woven/braided fabric structures, and the appropriate geometric properties can be defined by processing the micro-CT images of the fabric. Progressive damage is accounted for by treating the yarns within the textile reinforcement as UD composites, and assigning stiffness reduction to the resin in meso-scale UC. It is worth noting that to predict damage and failure at a macro-scale, the methodology as proposed here does not require specification of the failure criteria in a conventional sense, and material testing is not required for defining the macroscopic material response; however, mechanical test data can be used for model verification.

At present, the model development is being finalized by incorporating an appropriate progressive damage definition and rate dependency into the model. The extended description of the modelling process along with further validation and application examples will be pursued in future publications.

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